

THE DETERMINATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PERSONAL PROPERTIES AND BODY APPRECIATION OF PHYSICALLY DISABLED ATHLETES

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to find out the relationship between the physically disabled athletes' body persecution and personality traits. The sample of the study comprised a total 40 voluntarily participating athletes. Eysenck Personality Survey short form, of which validity and reliability have been done by Karancı and his friends in 2007, and Body Admiration Scale, of which validity and reliability have been done by Anlı and his friends in 2007, has been used as data collection tool. SPSS 20 Packet Programme has been used for analyzing the collected data. "Kolmogorov-Smirnov" single sample test has been applied to learn whether the data have a normal distribution or not. "Anova-Homogeneity of Variance" Test has been applied to detect the data homogeneity and it has been found out that data have normal and homogeneous distribution. Descriptive Statistic, Pearson Correlation Analysis and Regression analysis have been applied for analyzing the data. At the end of the Statistical Analysis, It has been found out that there is a negative direction relationship between body admiration score and neuroticism and the psychoticism scores.

Keywords: body admiration, personality, disabled, athlete

1. Introduction

There are more than one definition and theory of personality in the literature. In the most general sense, personality includes everything from A to Z that interests the person. The beginning of the personality is a long and uninterrupted process that starts from the time when a person enters into the mother's womb and continues until the end

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of his life (Tazegül, 2012., Güney, 2000., Hancerlioğlu, 1993, Geçtan, 2004). Cüceloğlu defines personality as a consistent and structured relationship form which is established by inner and outer environment that separates oneself from other people (Cüceloğlu, 2002).

Sport is an instrument in the socialization of individuals as well as allowing the individual to express their emotions and realize themselves through the exercises and games that a sport branch includes. Through the sport, individuals learn to release many negative instincts, mainly aggression, and keep them under control (Öztürk, 2007).

Sport is a form of behavior that meets basic needs while at the same time ensuring that the impulses arising from the individual's biological instinct are reached the target. The aim may be individual, social or economic. Sport is not only a physical activity; it is also an instrument in the socialization and integration into society of the individual. In that case, the interaction in the sports environment provides suitable opportunities for abreaction and emotional control. The individual participating in sportive activities has the opportunity to express her through exercises. It learns to control emotions such as aggression, anger, shyness, jealousy, which are described as negative behaviors, and negative emotions. Therefore, it has a positive effect on the adaptation process. At the same time, sport has a positive effect on neurovegetative nervous system, so it ensures this system to work in a balanced manner. It helps to overcome the excitement, aggression and irritability. The successes and goals achieved in the sport increase the self-confidence (Feist, 1990; Kuru, 2003).

There are a variety of ways that people can pursue to keep their bodies in shape, physically muscular, and look more elegant. It is foreseen that sports activities positively affect body perception. Physical activity and exercise enable people to have an ideal body structure by inserting their bodies in a certain way. Physical appearance is one of the most important issues that people of all ages, especially the younger generation, nowadays take in consideration. The physical appearance of an individual is often able to prevent his/her behavior and success. A woman's thin appearance or a man's muscular appearance is among the social values accepted by society. Ideal size and shape can be defined as proportional and healthy body at the same time. At this point, it is seen that the effect of body perception on women is higher (Er, 2015).

The concept of body perception was first discussed by Paul Schilder in 1920 as a psychological and sociological concept. The studies done before Schilder were usually limited to the perceptions related to corrupted body that may occur as a result of the brain damage. Schilder describes his sense of body as his own form that he has formed in the mind of man (Polat, 2007: 8; Dunham. 2002: 25).

The first written account of a body image disturbance was that of Ambroise Pare, the famous sixteenth-century surgeon, who reported in his phantom phenomena. Head, a neurologist in the 1920s, put forward the concept of the body schema. According to this, the body diagram constitutes a whole of *“the emotional cortex, which is composed of the past experiences and the present sensations”* (Dogan and Dogan, 1992: 1-2).

The past experience of the individual has an important place in the development of body sensation. The reactions that the individual has shown to his own body in the past and the individual receives from his/her environment about his body may influence the individual's sense of body development (Tazegül, 2016). The body perception which is usually perceived as a positive concept can have significant effects on an individual's self-esteem and confidence (Şanlı, 1991: 63).

There is a variety of ways that people can pursue in order to keep their bodies in shape, physically muscular, and look more elegant. It is foreseen that sports activities positively affect body perception. Physical activity and exercise enable people to have an ideal body structure by inserting their bodies in a certain way. Physical appearance is one of the most important issues that people of all ages, especially the younger generation, nowadays take in consideration. The physical appearance of an individual is often able to prevent his/her behavior and success. A woman's thin appearance or a man's muscular appearance is among the social values accepted by society. Ideal size and shape can be defined as proportional and healthy body at the same time. At this point, it is seen that the effect of body perception on women is higher (Er, 2015).

In the shortest sense, body image can be defined as our comment about the image we see when we look at the mirror. It expresses how the individual perceives his own body shape. People with negative body image think that they are overweight if they are not in fact. In addition, our feeling and perception how our body looks can be defined as our body image (Schilder, 1950).

The main aim of the study is to reveal the relationship between personal properties and body properties of physically disabled athletes.

2. Method

2.1 The Sample

The sample of the study was represented by a total of 40 physically disabled athletes from the branches of swimming, football, basketball and athletics who voluntarily agreed to participate in the study.

2.1 The Eysenck Personality Questionnaire-Revised Short Form (EPQ & EPQR-S)

The Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ, by Eysenck & Eysenck 1975) and 48-items short form of the same questionnaire, the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire-Revised Short Form (EPQR-S; Eysenck, Eysenck, & Barrett, 1985) was revised and EPQ & EPQR-S was formed.

2.2 The Body Appreciation Scale

The Body Appreciation Scale was developed by Anlı et al. in 2015. The five-point Likert-type scale was consisted of 10 items. The item's total correlation coefficient is between .31 and .76 (Anlı et al., 2015).

2.3 The Analysis of Data

For analyses of the data, Portable IBM SPSS Statistics v20 software package was used. "The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test" was applied in order to decide whether data has normal distribution, "ANOVA-Homogeneity of variance" was applied to test the homogeneity of variances, and it is observed that data is homogeneous and has a normal distribution. After this initial analysis, it was decided to use the parametric test method in statistical analysis of the data. For the analysis of data, the descriptive statistics, Pearson Correlation analysis and regression analysis were used to analyze the collected data.

3. Findings

Table 1: The Findings of Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Body Appreciation	38,9063	6,79354
Extroversion	3,9412	1,25387
Neurotic	3,3529	1,41169
Psychoticism	2,4571	1,46213

According to the results of descriptive statistical analysis, physically disabled athletes' body appreciation score was found to be (38,9063±6,79354), extroversion personality score was found to be (3,9412 ± 1,25387), neurotic personality score was found to be (3,3529 ± 1,41169) and psychoticism personality score was found to be (2,4571 ± 1,46213).

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

		Body Appreciation
Extroversion	Pearson Correlation	,328
	P	,077
Neurotic	Pearson Correlation	-,515**
	P	,003
Psychoticism	Pearson Correlation	-,486**
	P	,005

As a result of the correlation analysis carried out, it was determined that there is a negative relationship between neurotic and psychotic personality characteristics and body appreciation score of athletes in the sample group.

Table 3: Regression Analysis

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square		Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	,700 ^a	,490	,428		5,24370	
Model			Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression		659,350	219,783	7,993	,001 ^b
	Residual		687,409	27,496		
	Total		1346,759			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	47,026	4,807		9,783	,000
	Extroversion	,907	,838	,165	1,082	,289
	Neurotic	-2,288	,679	-,494	-3,369	,002
	Psychoticism	-1,501	,757	-,309	-1,983	,049

As a result of the regression analysis, statistically significant cause-effect relationship was found between neurotic and psychotic personality characteristics and body appreciation score of athletes in the sample group.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

According to the results of descriptive statistical analysis, body appreciation score of physically disabled athletes in the sample group was found to be (38.9063 ± 6.79354) while the extroversion personality score was determined higher than the neurotic personality score and the psychotic personality score. In the light of these data, it can be said that physically disabled athletes in the sample group are generally cheerful and social people. Because people who have developed extroverted personality love to communicate with people and they are usually cheerful people. It is thought that the one of the biggest factors is sport that physically disabled athletes can develop their characteristics of being extroverted personality. Because, as a result of literature review, many studies on personality and sports have been revealed that sports have an important role in an individual's socialization and self-confidence.

Tazegül (2014) carried out sports training on university students four days per week for 3 months. At the end of the study, it was found that there was a positive development in the personality of the students and an increase in their self-confidence and sense of responsibility. Kane (1964) discuss that athletes are safer and more emotionally stable compared to individuals not engaging in sporting events (transferred by Kuru, 2003).

Yapılan literatür taraması sonucunda, sporcuların beden algıları ve kişilik özellikleri üzerine As a result of the literature review, many studies were found to reveal the relationship between athletes' personal properties and body perceptions. However, it was observed that no study was found to reveal the relationship between physically disabled athletes' personal properties and body perceptions. Some of the studies that reveal the personal properties and body perceptions of physically disabled athletes:

Morgan found a level of neuroticism below normal standards among 12 US, 4 Canadian and 7 South African college student wrestlers attending Amateur Wrestling World Championship in 1966 (transferred by Tosunoğlu, 2008). Tazegül (2012) found that wrestlers' extroversion personality score was found to be $(=3.454)$, neurotic personality score was found to be $(=3.035)$ and psychotic personality score was found to be $(=1.930)$. Güven (1988) examined the psychic properties, personality characteristics, mental health characteristics, intelligence forms and levels of athletes engaged in freestyle wrestling. The athletes engaged in freestyle wrestling had higher scores in psychopathic, paranoid and hysteroid dimension than non-athletes. The wrestlers have more extroversion personality. A significant difference was found between wrestlers' concrete and creative intelligence and their dimension of extroversion. Tazegül (2015)

found that wrestlers' extroversion personality score was found to be (=3.523), neurotic personality score was found to be (=3.125) and psychotic personality score was found to be (=1.877). Tazegül (2016) set the score of body appreciation score of elite tennis players was found to be (40.9808). Tazegül (2016a) determined that the body perception level of bodybuilding athletes competing in 90 kg and below categories have at a better level than the other athletes.

As a result of the correlation analysis which was carried out to reveal the personality characteristics and body appreciation score of athletes in the sample, it was determined that there is a negative relationship between neurotic and psychotic personality characteristics and body appreciation score of athletes in the sample group. As a result of the regression analysis which was carried out to reveal the personality characteristics and body appreciation score of athletes in the sample, statistically significant cause-effect relationship was found between neurotic and psychotic personality characteristics and body appreciation score of athletes in the sample group. When this statistics is evaluated according to neurotic and psychotic personality characteristics and body appreciation, it is thought that this result is normal.

As a result of the study, it was determined that there is a negative relationship between neurotic and psychotic personality characteristics and body appreciation score of physically disabled athletes in the sample group. When the neurotic and psychotic personality scores of the athletes increase, their level of body dissatisfaction increases. The resulting statistic is thought to be normal. Because the individuals with developed neurotic and psychotic personality have a negative attitude towards the facts, because they are generally worried and the opposite types. In addition, in the literature review, no study was found that directly reveals the relationship between neurotic and psychotic personality characteristics and body appreciation of physically disabled athletes. Therefore, it is thought that this study will be a great contribution to the literature and set a more comprehensive example for the studies which will be done thereafter.

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